

OIL ECONOMY AND LABOUR SHIFT, THE MILIEU OF FOOD INSECURITY IN THE ONDO PROVINCE: A HISTORIC REVIEW - 1950-1985.

BY

¹Adu-Peters R. Olusola and ²Babalola Olatomide Emmanuel

*¹Department of History and Diplomatic Studies, Adeyemi Federal University of Education
Ondo Nigeria*

*²Department of History and International Studies, Bamidele Olumilua University of Education,
Science and Technology, Ikere, Ikere Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria*

CORESSRponding AUTHOR

Adu-Peters R. Olusola

**¹Department of History and Diplomatic Studies
Adeyemi Federal University of Education**

Ondo Nigeria

raliatsola@yahoo.com

+2347039000896

ABSTRACT

This study is a historical survey, it identified the major reason for the depleted food basket of the nation as the shift from major food crop production to oil economy beginning from the 1950s. The already educated young men who provided labour in support of their fathers at the various farms began to move to the urban centers for employment at the oil companies, leaving the food crops to suffer resulting in a major set back in food production. Nigerian youths left food crop farming to enjoy the national cake, thereby creating rural decay in which the old farmers solely grappled with the needed labour to keep the system in operation. This study made use of archival materials and oral interview conducted with Respondents in the study area. Books, journal articles, letters, memoirs and the Internet were the secondary source of data collection. Findings showed that labour flight from the Ondo Province since the 1950s, consequent upon oil economy, was principally responsible for paucity of food in the area. It elicited the veracity of the huge loss of healthy food items since the era of oil exploration as well as its irrecoverable impact on the the people in the study area. This study therefore suggested a more pragmatic economic policy towards agriculture that could lead to of opening up of fallow land to encourage the youth for food crop production farming for sustainable development.

Keywords: Oil Economy, Labour Shift, Milieu, Food Scarcity, Ondo Province.

INTRODUCTION

The history of Ondo Province, according to (Adinlewa 1952) was traced to 1915 under Sir Lord Lugard. It was a new name given to the areas located in the old Ondo area occupied by the Akure, Ondo, Ekiti, Owo, Akoko and Okitipupa groups. (Okajare 2004) corroborates that the Province was initially made up of four major Divisions known as Ondo Division, Owo Division, Okitipupa Division, Ekiti Division and later, Akoko Division. The late inclusion of Akoko as a Divisional entity was due to a long period of dominance of the place by foreign powers; beginning with Nupe belligerents up till 1897, when the Royal Niger Company took over and cleared the paths for effective colonial administration. During colonial rule, Akoko was administered directly from Kabba. In 1909, it gained partial autonomous judicial power which was later strangled by internal power tussles between the kings of Oka and Ikare towns. Akoko remained under the influence of Kabba up till 1st January, 1919 when it officially became a District under the Owo Division. At this period, there was a sort of diplomatic struggle between Owo and Akoko which continued up till 1st April, 1935, when full autonomy was granted to Akoko as a Division in the Ondo Province of South-western Nigeria. Beer (1976) described the indigenous people of Ondo Province to have subsisted on farming of food crops, fishing and craftsmanship prior to the oil economy, with the use of basic tools at different stages before the colonial influence, and the immediate sources of farm labour were from the family members, slaves and friends, through co-operative workforce. Ikuejube (2005) elicited that the oil producing area of Ilaje as other Yoruba

communities grew food crops such as maize, plantain and rice along the river banks while fishery remained dominant in their economic engagements.

Aghalino (2012) & Okpalaeke (2001) traced the history of oil exploration to the German Bitumen Corporation in the 1930s, when oil prospecting licence was issued to Shell BP in the oil producing area of Nigeria in 1937. Dike (1962) reported that the Oloibiri large quantity discovery in 1955 as well as Oketie (2008) indication that the Boma, Afam and Araromi Obu episodes significantly presented Nigeria as an oil producing nation-state. Hence, Exxon Mobil launched its operation by drilling about three deep wells in Lagos in 1955 and the first tapping was carried out by Shell BP in 1959 for commercial purpose.

Oil Boom and Labour Loss

The Oil economy triggered the migration of the workforce to the urban areas, thereby constituting a great economic challenge to national economy. A cursory look at the relevance of the agricultural sector stemmed from the postulation of Ajibefun & Akadiri (1999) that it contributed over sixty percent (60%) to the Gross Domestic Products of Nigeria in the 1960s, despite its dependence on its peasant farmers with the use of traditional methods of cultivation. Invariably, the farmers produced 70% for export purpose while the remaining was for basic consumption. Berry (1987), Davies (2014) as well as Agboola (1965) opined that a critical economic fallout of the foregoing was an unabated decline in the agricultural sector, consequent upon the new found oil economy, precipitated by changes in government economic policies in support

of oil market and exports that automatically encouraged labour flight.

Smith (1998) averred that labour flight was a pre-historic initiative that enhanced the movement of people from a particular location to new areas to engage in new human endeavour of better interest. Nyaugito (1999) further reported that the negative influence of the alarming rate of emigration of the virile Nigerian population in search of greener pastures in the urban areas rapidly undermining farm work and food crop production in Nigeria. According to Ikuejube (2005) & Olatunbosun (1975) many farmers depended largely on immediate labour which was often rendered by the young members of the farmer's family. This reduction in the labour force resulted in the unpredictably dwindling of the agrarian economy. Onitiri (1966), Adeoti (1989) & the United Nations Development Programme (1994) therefore opined that the provision of basic infrastructures and gainful employment for the people in rural areas will result in the reduction of rural-urban labour flight among the youths. In addition, Eide (1999) averred that the provision credit facilities and subsidy to the young farmers by the government could help retain them in the rural areas.

Another area of keen interest to this study was reiterated by Davies (2014) in his emphasis on the effect of farmer's old age on food crop production in Nigeria. He production.

Structural theoretical Analysis

The understanding of a traditional agrarian economy with modern intricacies (oil boom) is suitably projected along the interpretation of the structural functionalism theory. Generally inferred, Ritzer (2004) and other proponents of structuralism theory premised the functionality of the theory to the 1940s

opined that the aged farmers naturally recede to the weak population of the economic system as most of the farmers above 55 years were getting weaker and unwilling to work as food crop growers, especially when the farm was far from the house. A trajectory view of the ongoing, accentuates the position of Iretolu (2018), encapsulating the critical but pathetic condition of the existing farm settlement structure in Ondo Province. A situation whereby farmland was apportioned for mass production of cash crops, less was devoted to the production of food crops. It was observed that the original farmers were all dead, leaving the farms to the younger family members whose orientations are geared towards pursuing "more rewarding opportunities" in the oil companies. UNDP (1994) projection of the economic arm of United Nations commission for Africa elucidates that the population of the aged farmers would jump from 16.6 million to 28.6 million between 1995 and 2015, thereby rendering the potential mechanism of food production apparently elusive in the nearest future. This study therefore established that labour flight wrecked a seemingly unrecoverable havoc to the food production capability of Ondo Province. It also established the basis for labour loss in post-colonial food crop production among the people by bringing a strong nexus between labour loss and food crop

and 1950s, when the world was adjusting against the backdrop of the World war. A period when the whole world witnessed the consummated supremacy of strong state over the traditional societies. In other words, this theory explicitly aligns with the traditional society of Ondo Province focusing on the oil economy as the so called "determinant of the action of the people and of the society in

general.” The pattern invariably created a structural consequence for the enhancement of the newly found economy (Huaco 1986: 52). The interpretation for the above indicates that a wide lacunar in the traditional structure is created and structural functionalism theory emphasises an equilibrium meshed well for the interest of the traditional economy of Ondo Province for structural functionalism. The equilibrium according to Dean, (2001) & Miller (1993) brings a strong link between knowledge and power, looking beyond the dominance of the powerful state to integrate the norms of the traditional society of Ondo Province with the intricacies of the modern economy (oil), for a functional structuralism. On this note, Kilminster and Mennell (2000) & Kriekan, (2001) posited that both the objective and subjective elements of the old traditional economy (agriculture) and those of the modern economy (oil) be integrated logically to create a “multidimensional” economic relationship for societal benefits. In this case, rational choice with the help of the Economists to deal with the economic problems are quite inevitable. Structural functionalism is therefore considered most appropriate approach to deal with modern/structural challenges and food production and consumption in the traditional society of Ondo Province.

Labour Flight from Ondo Province

Okediji (1968) defines labour flight as the transfer of man-power from a particular location to the other. Labour flight in Ondo Province was principally precipitated by the oil economy and this was massively projected under the concept of “rural-urban drift.” Manyong, et al (2005) assert that labour flight took place between 1950 and 1969 while government policies between 1970 and 1985 eventually obliterated the home grown food sector, and the process

began with the influx of individuals who exchanged their labour with material wealth in the established farms of Ondo Province. Along the same vein, Adegeye (1974) reiterates that labour flight was exacerbated by the acquisition of western education which served as a major eye-opener to the young school leavers, who intentionally abandoned their farms and searched for jobs in the oil companies in Lagos and Delta axis. In fact, the period between 1950 and 1960 was remarkable for inward and outward movement of labour across southwestern Nigeria. Onitiri (1966) substantiated the dual course movement to the early remarkably migrations that resulted in the exchange of labour prowess for white collar jobs outside the rural environment in the 1950s for oil boom and cash crop business, consequently forcing a serious repression on food crop production, such that the Province lost its agile workforce to the newly found labour-driven enterprises. In other to source for alternative labour, Okediji (1965) establishes that migrant labourers were absorbed from among the Bendel, Epira and Igbo groups, by the indigenous farmers who had derived great satisfaction from the new farming system. Iretolu (2018) however elicits that in the 1970s, the hired labourers began to migrate back home to partake in the national cake from the oil boom, leaving farm work to suffer a generational setback which as persisted till today. The enormous effect of the neglect of the agricultural sector was stressed in Beer (1976) that the situation degenerated to the practice of continuous use of scarce and capital-laden daily labour, given the fact that the land lord farmers had lost their strength to old age and could no longer offer the required labour. This scenario was objectively criticized by Iretolu (2018), stating that the use of daily labour was capital intensive and could

retrogressively affect farmers' output when compared with the sufficient energy supplied under the labour of the settled workers.

Labour Flight and its Aftermath

By 1973, there was a paradigm shift of labour from the agrarian environment to oil economy. Oketie (2008) further highlighted that the high demand for crude oil led to the creation of several oil refineries at strategic locations across the country. Aghalino (2012) in corroborating this stated that the overt attention on crude oil economy recorded a high capital flow into the economy when it experienced multiple price increase of about 25.3 percent between 1970 and 1979. A consensus position of Williams (1980) & Oketie (2008) accentuated that the oil sector imbued over 162,000 barrels by the end of 1979. In other words, Adu-Peters (2011) posited that oil production in post-colonial Nigeria, with its antecedent of structural adjustment undermined the agrarian sector by attributing 90 % to oil derivation, 10% agriculture, out of which 6.6 % was allotted to cash crops and 3.4 % to food items such as hibiscus (*isapa*) for *zobo* drink, turmeric, ginger, garlic, cloves and plantain, excluding other tuberous crops such as yam, and cocoyam. Nigerian government thus stopped financing food crop production by devoting its total expenditures on oil and modern infrastructural development, and on this note, Adeoti (1979) averred that the structural change from agricultural to petroleum economy, particularly from the 1970s, when the former was neglected and relegated to the background led to massive rural-urban migrations at an unprecedented scale. Thus, the results of these changes, particularly in the 1990s indicate that a far greater number of people, more significantly in the urban areas, cannot adequately feed themselves and

are therefore faced with increased insecurity, widespread diseases and criminal activities.

The above claim was further accentuated by Agboola (1965) that in 1979, allotted money to the agricultural sector dropped from 5% to 3.2% while most young men were recruited into the transport businesses, such as railway stations and other government transport business. Clarke (1981) reported that between 1972 and 1980, food production per head fell by approximately 35-50%. Dorosh & Akanji (1981) substantiated that food imports rose to 250%, meaning that food cultivation as the traditional mainstay of the economy of Ondo-Ekiti had been strangled.

Adeoti (1989) claimed that the oil boom changed Ondo Province from a self-sufficient producer of food crops to being an “outward-looking buyer” of exotic food items which can be attributed to the immediate result of labour flight from Ondo Province that resulted in a fall in food crop production. The acute fall in food production necessitated the creation of ministries of agriculture and affiliates to sustain the food production sector by the government.

In order to adequately finance the agricultural sector, Davies, (2014) reported the establishment of Nigeria Agricultural and Cooperative Bank (NACB) in 1973 in major cities of Lagos, Abeokuta, Akure and Ibadan, to make loans accessible to small and privately owned farms. The loan scheme was eventually dichotomized to accede to the needs of farmers with substantial collateral (cash crop farmers). Three years after the establishment of NACB, special food projects were sponsored in partnership with the state government to aid rural farming, the project faced a gradual failure as a result of the poor land holding title (land tenure) (Clarke, 1981). Part of the measures at reinvigorating the food farming programme

included the adoption of River Basin Development Authority (RBDA) for water supply to the rural farmers in the Province.

Various western economic policies formulated by the expatriate companies were overtly beneficial to the oil explorers and to the detriments of food crop production especially in the Niger-Delta communities of Ondo Province. Ekong (1992) describes the western idea of agriculture support schemes inaugurated under the World Bank Agricultural Development Projects in same 1975 as a wrong approach that endangered structure, through its emphasis on a shift from traditional method of farming to the use of technological innovations known as Agricultural Development Project (ADP) to breed exotic seedlings against dependency on oil boom. Unfortunately, the ADP scheme is still struggled as a result of non-compliance of the soil with exotic method of food crop production. The challenge lingered till 1978 when Land Use Act was reviewed to facilitate rapid food crop production against the escalated food prices and scarcity (Berry 1989). The staggered food economy persisted till the global economic recession of the 1980s and its eventual demise under the Structural Adjustment Programme of 1986 of consistent export policy.

In spite of the various strategies at reconfiguring the food production sector, the elusive hydra-headed labour flight remained an unsurmountable clog to the successive programmes mounted by the various governments. On this note, Rentlinger (1983) observed that Nigerian government expended one thousand, fifty million naira (₦1,050,000) to export grains for feeding the Oil economy, had its enormous consequential effects on the agrarian communities of Ilaje and Ese Ondo. Foremost was the horrendous destruction of the ecosystem and an irrecoverable backlash on farm products and

growing population in 1980. Between 1970 and 1980, grains' importation accounted for over 62 % of Nigeria's total import in the same year. Agboola (1965) indicated a more worrisome occurrence of lowering of the prices of grains by the national government, making it more affordable to the urban population at the expense of the rural farmers. Williams (1976) also reported that the urban workers satisfactorily afforded the prices of food-stuffs due to the newly found jobs of well-paid salaries. The Importation of grains at considerably low prices undermined rural grain crops production, such that, dividends realized from their annual production and sales into the outside markets were leading to deficits and loss of interests in the business (Agboola 1965). Berry (1987) elicited that individual farmers in Ondo Province began to withdraw their invested capital and labour from local production of food crops. Effect of this withdrawal was noticed in the increase of rice imported by the Nigerian government from 1,700 tons in 1970 to 700,000 in 1979 (Berry 1987). The ugly trend persisted and it was recorded in recent years in a five-year fiscal policy of Nigeria government, as indicated in the table below that Nigerian government has seriously derailed in its efforts at ensuring food security between 2001 and 2005 respectively. Absence of food security and basic welfare noticeably exacerbated protest and social unrest among the virile population with reference to the oil producing area of Ilaje/Ese Odo where a good number of break-down of law and order were recorded.

Communal Banditry and Insecurity

fishing among the peoples. Olatunji (2024) reported that spillage of crude oil engendered labour flight from among the Molute, Abetobo, Erunona and other communities of Ese Odo due to underground exploration of

crude oil by the local and Atlantic expatriate companies, spearheaded by Chevron and Conoil. Protracted communal clashes of 1998/1999 between the Izon Arogbo and the Ilaje group was illustrated by Magi (2003) as an age-long fratricidal war precipitated by struggle over the control of natural resources (land and oil). The case of Akpatakubu oil community boundary dispute between the Ilaje and Izon continued to raise red flag in the historical annals of communal relations. Ikuejube (2005) & Olatunji (2024) reported, that there were series of unprovoked attacks from the youths of the concerned communities which often degenerated to loss of lives and disruption of economic activities on land and across the sea routes. The indigenous people of Ilaje believed that the expatriate companies connived with the federal government to explore and tap the oil resource without infrastructural

compensation. Hence, Ikuejube (2005) & Olatunji (2024) affirmed that these have resulted in increased unwholesome activities from pressure groups under different nomenclatures, such as the Ilaje Patriotic Front, the Ilaje Volunteer Services and the Ilaje Niger Delta Youth, agitating for environmental security and good welfare. A situation that automatically rendered most youths constantly reliant on social vices such as kidnapping, bunkering and perpetually indolent. From the foregoing, national insecurity, as a major bane to economic growth and development is an age long occurrence, traceable to the antecedents of oil boom and modernity in Nigeria, consequently, Nigerian youths are totally disoriented by capital economy, well exacerbated by oil explorations with its horrendous implications for the food basket of the nation.

Federal Budget and Actual Expenditure on Agriculture (Billion).

Fiscal year	Budget	Actual Expenditure
2001	17,575	15,916
2002	16,509	9,521
2003	14,908	8,917
2004	12,725	10,768
2005	11,516	11,847
Average	1.78%	1.67%

Source: Morgues (2008).

CONCLUSION

This study examined the connection between modernity and discovery of oil economy vis a vis the food productive capacity of the old society of Ondo Province, situating its research methodology to investigate the pattern of food production among the people and the significance of the antecedents of the oil economy on the workforce. The virile

population consequently neglected farm work and embraced better rewarding jobs in the cities of Lagos, Ibadan and oil refinery companies around Nigeria, leaving farm work in the hands of the aged population and few individuals who offered daily labour at the various farm steads. Awareness of dire need for food production to the political economy of Ondo Province requires a

meaningful attention geared towards revitalizing the agrarian sector to avert protracted food scarcity and hunger. A strong menace with its ravaging claws hovering around the potentials of Nigeria could be arrested by formulating pragmatic economic policies, targeted at massive food crop production at short and long distant cultivable areas in Ondo Province. For instance, Ministries of Agriculture, through policy makers can form workable rule to galvanise the abandoned land resources to launch food crop production. Such acres of land traversed Akure/Ondo/Ore roads where traces of colonial agriculture were seen as well as along Ore/Okitipupa/Araromi Obu Akure/Owo/Akoko and Ekiti roads.

Fundamentally speaking, The Nigeria National Petroleum Company refinery at Odigbo is totally moribund, rendering the acres of land, which should have been cultivated by the migrant farmers along the Ondo/Ore axis useless. Southwestern Nigeria acres of land used in the production of cash crops under the colonial agricultural scheme had been abandoned for many years and governments are yet to show concern for their functionality amidst the clamour for agricultural sustainability. Our governments need be worry of the precarious effects of modernity lest the entire populace begins to lose cultivable land to modern day cemetery and estate structures.

REFERENCES

- Adegeye, A. J. (1974) ‘Re-Examination of the Issues involved in the Farm Settlement Scheme of the Western State of Nigeria’, *OAS*, III, 1, New Series. pp. 79-88.
- Adeoti, J. A. (1989) ‘Economic Crisis in Developing Countries: The Food imension’, in *Ilorin Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, Vol. 1.
- Adinlewa, B.F.A., (1952) *Akure District, Progress, Problem and Possibilities* Ilepa, Ikare Akoko, Oladare Press, pp 3
- Adu-Peters, R. O. (2010) ‘World Trade Organisation’s Regulations on Nigeria’ Cocoa Export’ An Unpublished M.Phil Thesis Submitted to the Post-Graduate College, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife.
- Agboola, S. A. (1965) ‘The Collection of Agricultural Statistics in Nigeria: The Example of the Agricultural Censuses’, 1960-65’, *NAJ*, 2, 2 pp. 58
- Aghalino, S. (2012), ‘Oil Corruption and Underdevelopment in Nigeria’ in Bello-Imam I. B. *Deregulation of the Downstream Sector of the Oil Industry in Nigeria*, Ibadan, University Press.
- Ajibefun, I.A. and Akadiri A. (1999) ‘An Investigation of Technical Inefficiency of Products of Farmers Under the National Directorate of Employment in Ondo State’ in *Economic Newsletters*:6, pp 113
- Akanji, P. (1992), *Cocoa Marketing Under Nigeria’s Structural Adjustment Programme*, NISER Monograph Series No 1
- Beer, C. E. F. (1976) *The Politics of Peasant Groups in Western Nigeria*, Ibadan.
- Berry, S. (1987) ‘Oil and the Disappearing Peasantry: Accumulation, Differentiation, and Under development in Western Nigeria’, in Michael Watts (ed.) *State, Oil and Agriculture in Nigeria* (Berkeley, p. 208-9.
- Clarke, R. J. (1981) ‘Households and the Political Economy of Small-Scale Cash Crop Production in Southwestern Nigeria’, 51, 4, pp. 807-823.
- Davies, A.E. (2014), ‘Food Security Initiatives in Nigeria: Prospects and Challenges’ *Mimeograph* Department of Political Science, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.
- Dean, M. (2001) *Critical and Effective Histories, Folcault Methods and Historical*

- Sociology, In George, R. and Barry, S. *Handbook of Social Theory*, London, Sage 327-31
- Dike, K. (1962), *Trade and Politics in the Niger Delta*, London, Oxford University Press pp15-30.
- Dorosh, P. and Akanji, B. (1988) "Impacts of Exchange Rate Changes on the Cocoa-Food Crop Farming Systems of Southwest Nigeria", *Mimeo* Ibadan.
- Eide, A. (1999) "Globalization, Universalization and the Human Right to Adequate Food", in Ogunrinade, A. Oniango R. and May, J. (eds), *Not by Bread Alone*, Food Security and Governance in Africa, *Toda Institute for Global Peace and Policy Research*, South Africa, ABC Press.
- Ekong, E. E. (1992), *The Role of International Monetary Fund and World Bank in Nigerian Agricultural Policy* pp 65-92
- Gavin W. and Beer, C. E. F. (1976) "The Politics of the Ibadan Peasantry", in Williams (ed.), *Nigeria: Economy and Society* pp. 135-156.
- Ikuejube. G. (2005) *The Yoruba Fishing People of the Niger Delta*, Ondo, Olajesu Press
- Interview with Iretolu (2018) (Mr), (66 yrs), Cash and Food crop farmer, Agric. Farm Settlement, Okitipupa . Interview with Olatunji Adebayo, (2024) (PhD) (57 yrs) Son of the Soil of Ilaje Fishing Community
- Kriekan V. (2001), *The Age of Structuralism Levi Strauss to Foucault* New York, Columbia University Press. 452
- Kilminster, R. and Mennell, S. (2000), *The Blackwell Companion to Major Social Theorists*: Malden, Mass, Blackwell 609-612.
- Manyong, V.M., Ikpi, A., Olayemi, J.K., Yusuf, S.A., Omonona, B.T., Okoruwa, V. and Idachaba, F. S. (2005) "Agriculture in Nigeria: Identifying Opportunities for Increased Commercialization and Investment". IITA, Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Miller, R. (1993), 'Social and Political Theory< Class, State Revolution' in Terrell Carver (Ed.) *The Cambridge Companion to Marx*. Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- Nyaugito, H. (1999) Food Policy and the Impact on Food Security", in Ogunrinde, A. Oniang'o, R. and J. May (eds), *Not By Bread Alone. Food Security and Governance, Society Africa: Tore Institute for Global Peace and Policy Research*, n. p.
- Okajare, S.T. (2004) "Akoko-Owo Relations From the Earliest Times to 1935: A Study in Inter- Group Relations in Northeastern Yorubaland" An Unpublished PhD Thesis submitted to the Department of History and International Studies, Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba Akoko, 2004 pp 127-150.
- Okediji, O.O. (1965) "Some Socio-Cultural Problems in the Western Nigeria Land Settlement Scheme: A Case Study", *NJESS*, 7, 3 pp. 301-310
- Okediji, O. (1968), 'Some Structural Strains in the Change Agent System of the Western Nigeria Land Settlement Scheme', *NJESS*, 10, 3 pp. 393-394.
- Oketie, H. V. (2008), *Nigeria at a Cross Road, Oil and the Fragility of Multi-Ethnic State*. Port Harcourt, Harey Press.
- Okplalaeke, D. (2001), "A Crime Against Nature" *Tell Magazine* January, p8
- Olatunbosun, D. (1975), *Nigeria's Neglected Rural Majority*, Ibadan.
- Onitiri, H. M. A. (1966) "A Proposal for Nigerian Rural Development", *NJESS*, No 8, Vol. 1 pp3-8
- Rentlinger, S. (1983) "Food Security and Poverty in Less Developed Countries", in *Journal of Finance and Development*, Vol. 22, Nos.5, pp 7-11.

Smith D.W. (1998) “Urban Food Systems and the Poor in Developing Countries”, *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers, New Series*, Vol. 23, No. 2 Blackwell

United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), (1994) *Human Development Report*, New York: Oxford University Press.
Williams, G. (1980), “Ideologies and Strategies for Rural Development: A Critique”, in *State and Society in Nigeria* Idanre, p. 145.